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wooden clogs (VRVM 91145) (Q772)

shoes from Riga in the collection of the Museum of the History of Riga and Navigation

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Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	wooden clogs (VRVM 91145)	shoes from Riga in the collection of the Museum of the History of Riga and Navigation	

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[TextileBase Q772 preview.jpg](#)
1,280 × 533; 98 KB

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Artefacts as Material Sources of Traditional Clothing in Riga During the 18th and 19th Centuries

Data Description for TextileBase

Abstract

Years of creation: 2024–2025.

Institution: University of Latvia, Faculty of Humanities, Institute of Latvian History.

Funding: Grant “Contextualization of Traditional Clothing: Reassessing the Connection Between Riga and Latgale” (LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0023), Recovery and Resilience Facility project “Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia” (5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007).

Infrastructure provenance: The data sharing space system underlying TextileBase¹—from its technical architecture to its ontological design—was originally developed for the Open Music Observatory in the context of the Open Music Europe (OpenMusE) project. TextileBase was subsequently prototyped as an exploitation pathway to adapt and extend these results for cultural heritage and textile research, demonstrating their usability beyond the music domain [Open Music Europe 2023].

Keywords: dress history, Latvia, Riga, digital humanities, research data, data curation, knowledge base

Dataset:

Ieva Pigozne (2025). *Artefacts as Material Sources of Traditional Clothing in Riga During the 18th and 19th Centuries*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16995523.

Related dataset about secondary sources:

Ieva Pigozne (2025): *Visual and Written Sources on Traditional Clothing in Riga During the 18th and 19th Centuries*, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16995555.

¹ Antal, D – Pigozne, I. (2025). *Linking Garments to Knowledge: TextileBase as an Interdisciplinary Graph for Dress and Textile Research*. Preprint: [10.5281/zenodo.16914850](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16914850) [Unpublished preprint, please cite the final text and page numbering in Culture Crossroads (Vol.28) in 2025, expected publication Oct 2025 <https://culturecrossroads.lv/>] **TextileBase** is created with *ReprexBase*, a system developed in the *Open Music Europe* Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action (*Open Music Europe (OpenMusE) – An Open, Scalable, Data-to-Policy Pipeline for European Music Ecosystems*). Available: <https://doi.org/10.3030/101095295>) for the purpose of managing data about current and heritage music, musicians, and music-related information. It is based around the open source Wikibase database management system with a data sharing space configuration and a special data mode. More information about the system and its original use can be found in the bibliography.

Data Description

This open linked dataset brings together all known surviving material artefacts related to traditional clothing in Riga. These items, though numbering only a few, provide rare material evidence (Taylor 2015: 3-23) of garments once worn by the city's common people. Traditional clothing is defined here as garments and accessories characteristic of traditional dress (in contrast to the more cosmopolitan European urban fashions worn by townspeople) (Welters and Lillethun 2018: 163-168).

The data paper and the dataset of material sources on the traditional clothing of common people in Riga was created within the grant “*Contextualization of Traditional Clothing: Reassessing the Connection Between Riga and Latgale*” (LU-BA-PG-2024/1-0023) and financed by the Recovery and Resilience Facility project “*Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia*” (5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007).

Going back in time before the second half of the 19th century, only a very small number traditional clothing artefacts are known to have survived in Riga. The wearing of traditional dress in the city disappeared quite early, around the 1840s. Interest in collecting and preserving such garments for museums began only at the end of the nineteenth century (Kikuts 2016), by which time most of the evidence had already been lost.

The few surviving items – a jacket, two skirts, an apron, and two caps in the collection of the *National History Museum of Latvia* as well as three different wooden clogs in the collection of the *Museum of the History of Riga and Navigation* – were collected in Riga or its immediate surroundings and represent a period from the late eighteenth century to the early twentieth century. The twentieth century, although outside the chronological scope of our data collection, may be relevant in the case of the wooden clogs, whose dating is very broad and imprecise: from the nineteenth to the early twentieth century. The garments, however, are all dated to the nineteenth century, with the red woollen women's jacket belonging to the late eighteenth or early nineteenth century.

Evidence of traditional dress in Riga was never collected systematically, since at the time when such collecting took place, the main interest lay in traditional clothing from the Latvian countryside. This was because Latvian identity was being constructed primarily based on peasant traditions and rural cultural heritage (Kikuts 2016).

To partly compensate for the scarcity of surviving artefacts, the dataset also includes nine items discovered in archaeological excavations in the territory of Old Riga, which have survived in relatively complete form and clearly represent garments that were part of traditional

dress. These include several knitted stockings, a mitten, a glove, a brass crown, as well as two men's hats, all unearthed in excavation sites located in present-day Old Riga and dated to the late seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries. The excavations were carried out by archaeologists Viktorija Bebre and Andris Caune (Bebre and Caune 1990; Bebre 2004). Of these artefacts, only the crown can be identified as a female accessory, most likely worn by an unmarried young woman, while the two hats were worn by men. The wearers of the knitted stockings, mitten, and glove remain unknown.

Description of detail

TextileBase follows the **Wikibase data model**, in which each entity is represented as an **item** (a document in a document-oriented database). Each item contains a modular dataset: a self-contained set of knowledge statements that describe everything currently known about a given visual or textual source.

In archival or museological terms, our “level of description” is the artefact. It would be possible to record details (for example, describe parts of a garment, or its observed damages due to wear and tear over the centuries), but this was not the aim of this data collection. From the perspective of Wikibase, however, all of these are technically equivalent, therefore researchers can themselves suggest more detailed descriptions. The “level of description” is thus not a limitation of the data model but a decision in the curatorial practice.

The dataset was created on the **TextileBase** platform (<https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase>) allowing each artefact a separate entry with its own label and description and accompanying linked data. For each artefact included in the dataset, the following information is provided:

- the holding museum
- inventory number,
- place of collection or excavation,
- dating,
- wearer (if known),
- the material(s) from which it was made.

Often a photograph gives more information to the textile researcher than these data points. We have included in our dataset images from the *Museum of the History of Riga and Navigation*. Unfortunately, the *National History Museum of Latvia* does not support photographs of artefacts in its collection to be published online.

All the items are grouped into the collection **Traditional Clothing in Riga Collection** (TXB:Q764) and dataset **Artefacts as material sources of traditional clothing in Riga**

during the 18th and 19th centuries (TXB:Q763) that is a time-stamped snapshot (2025) of the collection, restricted to sources related to Riga. This dataset has a DOI (10.5281/zenodo.16995523) and includes 18 artefacts (TXB:Q770–Q787).

In this way, each item is simultaneously:

- a member of the collection (the ongoing research corpus), and
- a member of the published dataset (the frozen subset cited here).

This approach ensures maximum granularity, reusability, and citation stability, while preserving interoperability between human-readable description and machine-readable modular datasets. Individual entries are listed in the Annex by their label, each linked to its corresponding record in TextileBase, where the full description can be conveniently accessed.

Multimodality and copyright status of images

The artefacts that we describe usually predate intellectual property law, and therefore no restriction on depicting their design, surface patterns or outlook is present. At the time of creation there was no modern copyright law in the Russian Empire; the first provisions in that sense arrived with the 1828 Statute on Censorship, and a comprehensive Copyright Act followed in 1911. We do not see any reasons why photographic images of the artefacts could not be included in our dataset.

Contemporary photographs of the artefacts are available, which visually describe them as they can be seen in the 21st century. We have included in our dataset images from the *Museum of the History of Riga and Navigation*. These photographs are protected by institutional copyrights, and they can be used with attribution given to the museum together with the inventory number of the artefact. Unfortunately, the *National History Museum of Latvia* does not support photographs of artefacts in its collection to be published online, regardless of their copyright status.

Data structure

In developing this dataset within TextileBase, we adopted a Wikibase data model that follows established semantic patterns from multiple standards. For bibliographic and textual interoperability, we draw on DCTERMS; for museum collections, on CIDOC-CRM; for archival records, on Records in Context (RiC); and for provenance, on PROV-O. We also synchronize with globally used authorities such as GeoNames for geographical reference identification and the Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) for classification. This combination strikes a balance between ease of use for researchers, interoperability across disciplines, and

the possibility of importing from and exporting to large GLAM systems. For further details, please refer to our forthcoming publication (currently available in preprint²).

The dating of the object is made with the *has time* property, by default, with the precision of a year precision, like 1842. In the case of material sources, garments, usually such precise dating is not available. When have only approximate dating, for example, 1820-1850, the *has time* property is qualified with a *start time* (1820) and *end time* (1850) qualifiers. The *start time* qualifier property in this case refers the earliest like date, and the *end time* to the latest. The actual date entered the database is the midpoint of the time interval with a decade or a century precision mark. In a wide interval like 1820-1850, the entered number is 1835 displayed with a century precision, i.e., 19th century. The dating, if newer sources or evidence will allow more precise dating, can be later narrowed to decade, year, or in rare cases, a creation or collection day precision.

Regarding material sources, several important times and time intervals can relate to an artefact: the date of creation, the time period of use, the time of abandoning or collection, the time of discovery in the case of archaeological finds. TextileBase uses the *has time* property with qualifiers like *date of creation*, or *date of collection*. One artefact's provenance may be described with several points in time or time intervals.

When using these resources, please always cite:

Ieva Pigozne (2025). *Artefacts as Material Sources of Traditional Clothing in Riga During the 18th and 19th Centuries*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16995523.

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² Antal, D., & Pigozne, I. (2025). *Linking Garments to Knowledge: TextileBase as an Interdisciplinary Graph for Dress and Textile Research*. In Culture Crossroads (Preprint). TextileBase. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16914850>. You can also visit our presentations Antal, D., Pigozne, I., Gábor, K., & Fredercio, A. (2025). TextileBase: Introduction. TextileBase Seminars 1, National Laboratory for Digital Humanities, ELTE, Budapest. TextileBase. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16937140>

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Annex

For example, **TXB:Q771** resolves to <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Item:Q771>.

Researchers who wish to fetch the data for reuse in their own systems can retrieve the same entity in multiple serializations by changing the URL to:

- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q771.ttl> for Turtle,
- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q771.nt> for N-Triples,
- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q771.rdf> for RDF/XML,
- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q771.jsonld> for JSON-LD, or
- <https://reprexbase.eu/textilebase/Special:EntityData/Q771.json> for JSON.

Entry	Label
txb:Q770	wooden clogs (VRVM 52204)
txb:Q771	leather clog with wooden soles (VRVM 88405)
txb:Q772	wooden clogs (VRVM 91145)
txb:Q773	crown of brass (VRVM 41647)
txb:Q774	woollen stocking (VRVM 185483/1)
txb:Q775	mitten (VRVM 185483/5)
txb:Q776	woollen stocking (VRVM 185483/11)
txb:Q777	woollen stocking (VRVM 189074/2)

txb:Q778	glove (VRVM 177915/34)
txb:Q779	felted hat (VRVM 177915/85)
txb:Q780	fragment of a stocking (VRVM 177915/86)
txb:Q781	knitted woollen hat (VRVM 179158/10)
txb:Q782	festive skirt (CVVM 10441)
txb:Q783	festive skirt (CVVM 10448)
txb:Q784	festive jacket (CVVM 10514)
txb:Q785	winter peaked cap (CVVM 12608)
txb:Q786	apron (CVVM 14812)
txb:Q787	fur cap (CVVM 5677)